

TRAINING VOLLEYBALL TECHNIQUES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation: Volleyball is one of the main integral parts of the content of the physical education curriculum and extracurricular activities, as well as physical education and health activities. Volleyball technique includes a set of techniques with which the game is played. Considering the specific nature of the game of volleyball, possession of impeccable technique is crucial in achieving high results.

Key words: volleyball, technique, serve, pass, attacking blow, students.

Introduction. Volleyball is one of the main integral parts of the content of the physical education curriculum and optional classes, as well as physical culture and health activities. Special attention is paid to achieving a training effect from the use of volleyball equipment to improve speed, movements of increased amplitude, speed-strength qualities, development of general and special endurance. In the process of passing the training material on volleyball, one of the dominant aspects is the use of the means of this game in the health direction, to monitor the state of one's body and the changes that occur after using the means of playing volleyball as a physical load [1, 3, 4].

Volleyball is an interesting, dynamic, exciting sports game. Volleyball lessons can be called one of the most effective means of improving a person's physical fitness and sports health. The technique of playing volleyball is characterized by a variety of techniques performed in conditions of movement on the playground. That is why volleyball players must be able to perform ball receptions and offensive shots, blocking, passing the ball [2, 4, 5].

Given the fact that there are works that indicate a direct proportional relationship between physical development, the morpho-functional state of the body and general physical fitness, it is possible to assert the possibility of influencing the technical fitness of students engaged in volleyball sports sections through improvement they have certain physical qualities.

In view of this, the technology of game direction on the example of basketball, proposed by T.A. Bazylyuk, deserves attention. According to the author, the use of such a program in the process of physical education of female students of higher educational institutions improves their physical qualities - speed of reaction and coordination. According to the researcher, the use of such technology in the process of physical education of female students also contributes to learning the technique of possession of the ball [7, 9, 10].

Chernov L.Ya. highlighted the main technical actions necessary to master the game of volleyball: serving, receiving, passing the ball, attacking shot, block and rollover (a technical defensive technique when an attack is impossible). In order to develop the physical qualities necessary for this sports game, the author suggests using exercises aimed at developing speed, dexterity, flexibility, strength, explosive power, etc. in the training process [6, 8].

Volleyball competitions require athletes to show courage, determination, endurance, and the ability to overcome difficulties, and strict adherence to the rules helps foster organization and discipline.

Modern volleyball is a combination game that takes place at a high pace, attacks develop quickly, interactions of players near the net are complex. They must be able to switch from attack to defense in an instant. Such an instant change of situations is determined by the rules of the game. This is a game that won the hearts of many millions of people of our planet on all continents without exception. Extremely quick change of attacking and defensive actions - in each draw you can trace all the components of the game: serve-reception-pass-attack-block-reception and there are many variations, so volleyball is always interesting. There is no time

for long thoughts and hesitations in this game. Assessment of the situation, making the right decision and its implementation should be performed while the ball is flying [11,12, 14].

Volleyball technique includes a set of techniques used to play the game. Perfect technique creates favorable conditions for successfully solving game tasks in defense and attack and is based on the natural coordination of human movements. Only in this case, it is possible to achieve the efficiency of actions in the game, economical expenditure of forces during the entire meeting.

Taking into account the specifics of the game of volleyball, mastering impeccable technique plays a crucial role in achieving high results [13, 15, 16].

The technique of playing volleyball consists of the main game techniques and methods of their interaction, which are necessary for conducting the game. Various alternations of movements, which a volleyball player possesses, characterize his technical preparation. The technique of the game is divided by its characteristics into: the technique of the game in defense and in attack. The technique of attack includes: moving, serving, passing the ball, attacking shots.

Movement is the player's movements by stepping, jumping, running to choose a successful place to perform a specific technical technique. The player can move towards the ball with normal or slow steps.

If the distance between the player and the ball is large, or the ball flies fast enough, the volleyball player runs to the ball, makes a jump, or picks up the ball as it falls. In modern volleyball, serving is used not only to start the game, but also as an effective means of attack, with which it is difficult for opponents to organize offensive combinations.

There are power, targeted and gliding serves. Accurate execution of the serve makes it much more difficult for the opponent to receive it. As a rule, a lot of attention is paid to this element in training. Application of pitches due to the speed of the flying ball (power pitch), accuracy (aimed pitch), changes in trajectory and

flight (gliding pitch). It has been proven that teams with more aggressive pitching achieve better results.

Offensive shot - a technical technique of attack, which consists in the fact that the player moves the ball with one hand to the opponent's side above the upper edge of the net. When attacking, the kick is performed as follows: a jump from a standing position or from a run, a kick, a landing. To jump from a run, you need to push off with one or two legs, from a standing position - only with two legs. By performing a two-legged push-off while running, the player gains the speed necessary for a high jump.

Passing the ball is a technical technique by which the ball is directed above the top edge of the net for an attacking shot. Timely access to the ball and correct starting position are a mandatory condition for passing.

Transfers are short (within one zone), medium (from zone 2 to zone 3) and long (from zone 2 to 4). Gears can be low (up to 1 m high), medium (up to 2 m) and high (over 2 m). When performing high and long gears, the work of the legs is more active. Short transfers are best performed in a jump, this is a difficult technical technique, because it is performed in an unsupported position.

The development of dexterity in volleyball players is primarily related to the symmetry of movements, the uniformity of their efforts when receiving and passing the ball. Agility also depends on the volleyball player's ability to control his body 384 when performing various falls, rolls, when attacking and blocking the ball. It is also necessary to use special exercises for the development of strength, speed, jumping, endurance, dexterity and flexibility in volleyball classes. Means of strength development should be exercises of a dynamic nature with a moderate load. Exercises with weights of one's own weight (squats, jumps, push-ups, etc.) are mainly used, as well as useful mobile games that require short-term speed and strength stress. You can also use exercises with external weighting (for this, stuffed balls, dumbbells, balls are used). All these exercises will increase the level of

physical training, in particular, speed, strength, agility. These qualities play an important role in defensive and offensive actions.

All innovative approaches in sports training are aimed at achieving the most positive result. During the game, attacking from the back line is used more often, and not only from the first zone, but also from the fifth and, especially, from the sixth. Backline players are often included in the attack when the passing player is also in the backline, i.e. the fourth striker. When playing defense, players often cover their blockers with a front line player who does not participate in the block and players in the first and fifth zones.

Conclusions. A qualitatively new level of playing volleyball depends on the rational use of innovative approaches to technical training in the training process of students. Means based on the proportional application of various elements of game technique are considered effective. After analyzing the data of the attack and defense techniques, it can be concluded that the rational technique of the game has been mastered perfectly. Solving this problem makes it much easier to solve other problems.

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